

ASSESSING THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN DIGITAL SUPPLY CHAINS AND THE SELECTED DIMENSIONS OF LEAN MANUFACTURING: AN EMPIRICAL STUDY FROM KSA

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this research was to examine the effect of digital supply chains (DSC) on lean manufacturing (LM), which was evaluated on the basis of seven different metrics: Just in Time (JIT), Continuous Improvement (CI), Autonomation, Total Productive Maintenance (TPM), Value Stream Mapping (VSM), Cellular Manufacturing (CM) and Single Minute Exchange of Die (SMED). The construction firms in Saudi Arabia were selected to provide a sample of the population and to collect the data needed for the study. The data was collected using a convenience sampling strategy. The proposed model and research hypotheses were validated through the use of regression analysis. The findings showed that the digital supply chain (DSC) positively affected the key performance indicators of lean manufacturing (LM). The results of this study provide evidence for the efficacy of

digital supply chains, which are expected to significantly raise companies' bottom lines. It will also aid business leaders in a variety of resource allocation and investment choices along digital supply chains, with the ultimate goal of maximizing profits while decreasing costs.

Key words: Lean Manufacturing, Digital Supply chains, Regression, Just in Time, Continuous Improvement, Autonomation

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1. INTRODUCTION

The phrase "digital transformation" is used to describe the widespread adoption of electronic devices and the resulting shifts in how people interact with one another and the world around them (Gimpel et al., 2018). It opens up fresh possibilities for businesses as well as the supplier chain procedures (Al-Alwen et al., 2022; Eldahamsheh et al., 2021). Increased organizational value can be achieved through adaptable supply chain strategies and practices thanks to digital transformation and the fourth generation of industrial evolution (Tariq et al., 2022b). Complete-to-complete communication along the chain of supplies, made possible by the digitization inside supply chains, give businesses an edge by helping them adapt quickly to shifting customer demands (Porter&Heppelmann 2015).

The importance of DSC is growing in industrial organizations because of the profound effects they have on the day-to-day operations of retailers, manufacturers, distributors, and logistics providers, and more specifically on the management of inventory across various sales channels (Yearling, 2018). The notion of "DSC" has recently drew the interest of business leaders and specialists. Recent academic buzzwords like "big data" and other related topics have contributed to its meteoric rise in popularity (Alshawabkeh et al., 2022). Theoretical literature on digital supply chains, however, has different points of view. It shows that the field's development is not entirely clear, suggesting that more study is required in this area. A gap in the management literature on digital supply chains has become apparent. The underlying structure of this topic and the associated concerns still need to be elucidated. As technology and the digital sphere advance, businesses are better able to streamline their operations and keep the lines of communication open with their suppliers and potential clients.

Rapidity, reliability, global connectivity, intelligence, transparency, scalability, and many other advantages have all been linked to digital supply chains (Aityassine et al., 2021; Al-khawaldah et al., 2022). Digital transformation technologies improve supply chain connectivity, productivity, and agility, as confirmed by Kittipanya-In Ngam, & Tan (2020). However, there are many obstacles to overcome and specialized resources must be allocated as businesses shift to digital supply chains from the conventional chain of supply. Despite digital technology's usefulness in supplying big data systems, these systems presented significant challenges for food supply networks as the end Customer turned into better knowledgeable and more media-savvy. Digital supply chain technology can reduce costs by reducing waste, labor, and inventory, but there is little agreement on how to achieve these goals among supply chain participants (Al-Nawafah et al., 2022).

Increasing output and quality per unit of money spent on goods is a primary goal of many modern businesses, so lean manufacturing (LM) is increasingly being adopted (Sharma et al., 2021). To prove value from the perspective of the customer and reduce manufacturing waste, lean manufacturing practices emphasize the maintenance of a continuous flow based on the withdrawal of non-essential activities (Saxby et al., 2020). Just in time (JIT), autonomy and total production maintenance (TPM) (via mapping of value flow), as well as kaizen (constant improvement) are all tools used in lean manufacturing (CI). All of these methods are implemented by businesses that value adaptability in their production lines (Andreadis et al., 2017; Garza-Reyes and associates, 2018). Researchers found scant books on how digital supply networks affect the implementation Among the five waste-reducing procedures of lean manufacturing. According to Haartman et al. (2021), incorporating digital technologies into production is key to achieving lean manufacturing. Known as lean manufacturing product inflexibility, is a work environment strategy that seeks to continuously improve and enhance the production system by reducing or eliminating wasteful steps and activities (Maama et al., 2021).

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

2.1 Digital Supply Chains (DSC)

The notion of digital technologies is relatively recent and is still maturing. The incorporation of these innovations modifies conventional business processes. That's why they have an impact on the economy. DSC have impressive capacities for information processing and communication via digital platforms that facilitate effective collaboration with supply chain partners. The digitalization of supply chains lends uniformity to both production and consumption. The use of digital technologies has simplified and standardized many aspects of the chain of supplies, starting with the processes to the goods to the activities themselves. It creates novel product value, which increases the product's desirability among online buyers (Agrawal&Narain, 2018). The DSC's primary objective is the coordinated process organization in the supply chain. Digital models, procedures, and apparatuses form the basis for these. New business activities are made more mobile and physical goods are transported more quickly thanks to the advent of digital transformation technology. Thus, supply chain activities are impacted.

The notion of "e-supply chain" includes the term "digital supply chain" (Shahin et al., 2022). Supply chain operations in businesses benefit from digital tools (Vendrell-Herrero and colleagues, 2017; Wang and Lu, 2016). Because of this, Tools for digital transformation are crucial to the overall functioning of the supply chain. However, businesses face a number of potential challenges and risks (Xue et al., 2013). E-commerce is crucial to digital transformation, but it is also a costly tool to develop and implement (Tanoos, 2017; Chowdhuryetal., 2018). The price tag associated with integrating digital tools into operational supply chains is another barrier that businesses must overcome.

New technologies can be thought of as electronic supply chain management. Chain of supply practices are evolving as a result of these technological advancements. Due to the transformation, DSC is a team effort made up of various projects that all work together to facilitate transformation within businesses. According to Queirozetal (2019), a DSC is a collection of ICT assets that can be used for various purposes. It's used within a company's intranet to facilitate the transition from paper to electronic processes. To further cut costs and boost output, businesses are employing a combined digital and physical activity model. DSC is also used for supply chain collaboration with various suppliers. It is "the smarts of the right technological system." Supporting interaction between supply chain partners, this system requires the elimination of big data and the efficient use of hardware, software, and digital networks. Because of the increased value it provides, products and services can be distributed to consumers more rapidly and at lower cost (Büyüközkan&Göçer, 2018). Researchers across disciplines agree that it's crucial to have a thorough grasp of the concept of "digital supply chains." The shift to digital supply chains using block chain results in increased security and lower costs, as confirmed by Kurpjuweit et al. (2021).

People can easily and cheaply manage any data that pertains to them thanks to digital technology for information consists of instruments that offer Internet-based sources and information. A laptop, desktop computer, or tablet computer is required for use of digital information technologies. In human resource management, "digital HR" refers to the use of web technologies (Shamout et al., 2022). Employees need to learn new skills as digital

transformation introduces novel processes and potentially new types of work. Employees need to be taught new methods that take advantage of information technology and software programs. For this to work, upper-level management must be fully behind the idea and willing to commit resources to seeing it through (Berber et al., 2018).

2.2 Lean Manufacturing (LM)

spartan administration is an approach to organizational and social management that emphasizes effectiveness and seeks to get rid of trash through minimizing the gap in between the value created internally and that which is brought in from outside (Shah & Chauhan, 2021). The elimination of these bottlenecks in the system gives the company a leg up in the market by enhancing operations and productivity throughout the supply chain (Moyano-Fuentes et al., 2020). The term "Lean Manufacturing" is used by modern businesses to describe the desire to improve competitiveness through the introduction of new value while simultaneously eliminating wasteful practices (Novais et al., 2020). Among the greatest ways to boost efficiency at work is to encourage adaptable thinking (Nicoletti, 2013). The Toyota Motor Corporation of Japan coined the phrase "Lean Manufacturing" during Second World War.

The Toyota Production System was established as a means by which Toyota could determine the most effective means of carrying out operations and integrating integrating industrial processes into thorough, integrated operations (Osman et al., 2019). Most importantly, when applying Lean Manufacturing concepts, the tools are autonomy, VSM, CI, JIT, and TPM used to improve organizational performance (Andreadis et al., 2017).

2.3 DSC and LM

The efficiency of a business and its capacity to compete depends increasingly on its supply chains and the methods used to manage them (Ataseven & Nair, 2020). Due to implementing effective strategies for supply chain management leads to a variety of measurable gains in operational outputs like efficiency, inventory reduction, customer satisfaction, product quality, cost, and turnaround time (Sharma, et al. 2021). Several studies have shown that implementing digital supply chains can boost an entity's internal business sector efficiency in addition to the supply chain's overall efficiency (Tortorella et al., 2017; Marodin et al. 2017). The advantages, disadvantages, and challenges of implementing digital supply chains are discussed in detail in a recent paper by Büyüközkan and Göçer (2018). To ensure that enable Industry 4.0's digital supply chain capabilities, Quierez et al. (2019) identified six success components.

There has been a lot of attention paid to the importance of implementing DSC in previous research. Research on the possibilities and perils of digital transformation in production processes can be found throughout the administrative literature on production management. Many studies confirmed the need for additional study on this topic, and their findings point to the application of digital technologies in manufacturing for developing production proofs and prototypes for products (Meissner et al. 2018).

Companies, as confirmed by Martinez (2019), are actively seeking to digitalize their supply chains. They are also constantly working to improve their technological capacities for managing their supply chains (Martinez, 2019). The shift to digital and the use of Industry 4.0 technology in digital networks of supplies give businesses improved error prediction and detection capabilities. Thomas et al. (2018) note that the adoption of performance-enhancing techniques is still a goal for many organizations. The effects Building digital supply chains using the six instruments for lean manufacturing were uncovered in a study by Haddud and Khare (2018). The research found the use of digital supply chains help improve the efficiency of manufacturing lean techniques. Because of the high-quality tools utilized by digital supply chains, businesses are better able to reduce waste during production. The lack of research into the connection between the technology of digital transformation and the implementation of industrial lean manufacturing techniques firms has been confirmed by a number of earlier studies (Al-Alwan et al., 2022; Kolberg et al., 2017).

2.3.1 JIT Production System

The JIT production system, a central tenet of Lean Manufacturing, was the focus of this research. Production activity management and control is a modern management philosophy (Forza and Filippini 2016). It has been used for quite some time as a method of administration. According to (Kurilova-Palisaitiene&Sundin, 2018), just-in-time (JIT) is a method of process enhancement strategy that seeks to reduce the impact of inefficient, time-consuming, and randomly occurring procedures. Along the entire supply chain, JIT facilitates information sharing, decision making, and coordinated action by reducing lead times (HofmannandRüsch, 2017). By fulfilling routine orders in small quantities, businesses can save money on transportation and storage space by employing Just-in-Time (JIT) logistics (Goodarzi&Zegordi, 2018). The way in which businesses implement JIT strategies is undoubtedly influenced by the growing importance of digital transformation tools in the supply chain (Nowicka, 2017).

Hypothesis1: Digital supply chains has significant effect on JIT production system of Lean Manufacturing

2.3.2 Continuous Improvement (CI)

CI is the method of operation (Mirihagalla, 2020). It's a collection of techniques focused on creating and maintaining processes, constantly training staff, developing novel approaches to work, and actively seeking out and fixing errors as soon as they're spotted.

CI is a method for lean operations (Orzen& Bell, 2016) that entails a collection of actions for fostering the perpetual growth and improvement of work procedures through routine employee education, novel approaches to work, and rapid error identification and fixing (Krishnan, 2016). Improvements in efficiency are a primary goal of CI efforts. The goal of efforts to digitalize networks of supplies is to equip companies having advanced technical tools that improve their capacity to manage supply networks smoothly and efficiently. More digital features are appearing in newly improved areas of organizations as a direct outcome of CI initiatives (Martinez, 2019).

Hypothesis 2: Digital supply chains has significant effect on Continuous Improvement system of Lean Manufacturing

2.3.3 Autonomation

Lean Manufacturing relies heavily on and relies on autonomy (failure prevention) as a core practice (Garza-Reyes et al., (2018); Kolos, 2017). When an abnormal or defective condition occurs, the production process is halted by the Autonomation, which can be operated automatically or manually (Aslan et al., 2016). Today's machines are built with autonomation built in, so they can fail or shut down if they detect something out of the ordinary. Autonomation's current uses aren't restricted to shutting down machines when they break. This method of automation is quite comprehensive and ingenious. To be truly autonomous, a manufacturing facility must implement a comprehensive automation strategy, including a sequence of steps to automate fabrication and assembly operations, and a method for overseeing the routine interactions between humans and machines. This adheres to the goals of the lean manufacturing movement, which seeks to minimize or eliminate any step in the production process that is not directly related to increasing the value to the customer (Adjeit. Al. 2015).

Hypothesis 3: Digital supply chains has significant effect on Autonomation system of Lean Manufacturing

2.3.4 Total productive maintenance (TPM)

Equipment maintenance is another area where TPM shines, allowing for smoother production with fewer breakdowns and fewer injuries (Pandey et al., 2021). If you want to save money, make better use of your technology, and improve your workplace's ergonomics, all you need is a simple tool (Gidwani & Dangayach, 2017). (Habidin et al., 2018).

TPM is a comprehensive system for maintaining machinery in order to create a risk-free, defect-free, and uninterrupted production environment (Pandey and Raut, 2016). Equipment utilization can be stabilized through the use of TPM, which is why it is considered a key lean practice (Thanki et al., 2016). (Gidwani and Dangayach, 2017). TPM is useful for addressing monetary, technological, and workplace concerns (Habidin et al., 2018). Daily activities involving the entire workforce are the foundation of Total Productive Maintenance (TPM) (Kaur et al., 2013).

Hypothesis 4: Digital supply chains has significant effect on Total Productive Maintenance system of Lean Manufacturing

2.3.5 Value Stream Mapping (VSM)

VSM is a straightforward system that aids in monitoring the circumstances as they stand now additionally comparing it to predetermined criteria and employs a wide range of indicators and placards to manage people and procedures (VM) (Kurpjuweit et al. 2021; Thomas et al., 2018).

VSM is a tool used in lean manufacturing that compares the current state to predetermined targets (Kumar and Kumar, 2016). VSM is a method of managing people and

activities through the application of several signs, signals, and controls (Thomas, 2018). Operations management routinely makes use of VSM, especially in the context of initiatives for process improvement (Beynon-Davies and Lederman, 2017). Virtual supply chain management (VSM) has emerged as a useful tool for streamlining global chain of supplies (Murata and Katayama, 2016). VSM has become ingrained in lean manufacturing because it is consistent Given its foundational fundamentals (Koskela et al., 2018). Within this research, we analyze how the rise of digital supply chains may affect VSM procedures used in lean manufacturing settings.

Hypothesis 5: Digital supply chains has significant effect on Value Stream Mapping system of Lean Manufacturing

2.3.6 Cellular Manufacturing (CM)

In cellular manufacturing (CM) systems, Products are organized into product families, sometimes referred to as part families, in order to be manufactured on manufacturing cells, which are sets of machines arranged together on the shop floor (Iranian, 1999; Ham et al., 1985). Cellular manufacturing is a method that combines the adaptability of the employment agency with the effectiveness within the flow shop. Production systems can reap additional financial benefits from producing in smaller quantities using unit-by-unit methodology (Lin, Ying, and Lee (2009); Jeon&Leep, 2006).

Improved throughput and product quality are just two of the many benefits of implementing CM (Iranian, 1999; Ham et al., 1985). CM also cuts down on time spent on machine setup. Since the benefits of CMS are essential in today's global markets, CM have been linked to advanced production systems like JIT production and flexible manufacturing systems (Ebrahimi et al., 2016).

Hypothesis 6: Digital supply chains has significant effect on Cellular Manufacturing system of Lean Manufacturing

2.3.7 Single Minutes Exchange of Die (SMED)

Shingo (1985) created SMED, which stands for Quick changeover of tools, which can be used in any type of industrial setting and by any device to drastically cut down on setup times. The SMED was established as the shortest amount of time required to switch from one type of production activity to another between the time the last piece of one lot was made and the time the first piece of the next lot was made (Shingo, 1985). Before the SMED approach was developed, producing in bulk was the most effective method of reduce the time machines spent inactive while configuring, thus reducing the cost of setup time per unit. When inventory expenses were comparable to the expenses of idle equipment while the switch was being made of tools, Min and Pheng (2007) concluded that this was the optimal quantity for each production lot. Toyota ran into this issue because vehicle inventory costs were so high. Before this issue, cutting down on setup times was the best way to keep production losses to a minimum (Shingo, 1985). As a result, reducing the time it takes to make adjustments in production would allow for a smaller target output, thereby reducing associated costs.

Since It's essential to determine the bare at least for every batch of manufacture, the question of the optimal amount of the production lot persists. There are additional upfront expenses related to stock when manufacturing in bulk. Large-scale production becomes unprofitable once we factor in the opportunity cost of capital on top of the inventory cost.

Hypothesis 7: Digital supply chains has significant effect on Single Minute Exchange of Die system of Lean Manufacturing

3. OBJECTIVE

- To examine the impact of online shopping chains (DSC) regarding lean manufacturing (LM) in Saudi Arabia
- To propose a conceptual framework showing the connection between supply networks that use digital technology (DSC) and dimensions of lean manufacturing (LM) in Saudi Arabia
- To conduct an empirical analysis to validate the proposed framework showing the connection between supply networks using digital technology (DSC) and dimensions of manufacturing lean (LM) in Saudi Arabia

4. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

A conceptual framework, depicted in Fig. 1, is built based on the factors that were discovered in the literature and presented In the earlier part.

Figure 1: Conceptual framework

5. RESEARCH METHOD

Companies in the construction sector were chosen as a proxy for the population of interest and as a primary informational source for this investigation. We first got approval from higher authority at those companies to collect employee contact info and job titles before we reached out to anyone about taking the survey. Convenience sampling was used because it fit within both the research budget and time constraints. E-mail was used to disseminate the research questionnaire to participants. 595 questionnaires were sent out to employees in middle and operational management. There were 471 completed surveys returned. 13 of these responses, however, were disregarded because they were either incorrectly marked or lacked necessary information upon closer inspection. In the end, 458 complete and practical surveys were collected, for a response percentage of 76.97%.

A cover letter was provided with the research questionnaire that explained the study's anonymity and confidentiality guarantees and stressed that participation was entirely optional. The use of categorical control variables was discussed (gender, age, education, experience). Digital supply chain metrics and Lean Manufacturing indicators were also included in two separate sections. The answers were determined with a Likert scale of five, with "strongly disagree" at the lowest end and "strongly agree" at the highest, with "moderately agree" in the middle at the "3" mark.

6. RESULT AND ANALYSIS

6.1 Respondents' Demographic Profile

Table 1: Demographic Profile of the respondents

		Freq uenc y	Valid %			Frequen cy	Valid %
Gender Profile	Male	446	97.4	Education (highest level)	Diploma in Engineering	11	2.4
	Female	12	2.6		UG/PG in Engineering	344	75.1
Age Profile	21-29 years	125	27.3		Post- Graduate/ Master's Degree	33	7.2
	30-39 years	169	36.9		Graduate	70	15.3
	40-49 years	116	25.3	Working Experience in years (total)	3-5 years	136	29.7
	50 years and Above	48	10.5		6-8 years	228	49.8
					9-11 years	85	18.6
					12 years and more	9	2.0

It was determined that 446 males accounted for 97.4% of the correct responses, while 12 females accounted for 2.6% of the rest of the responses, for a total of 458 correct responses. 75.1% of respondents have UG/PG degree in engineering, 15.3% have a simple graduate degree, and 7.2% have a PG or higher in another field. According to the age group analysis, 64.2% of the sample fell into the "21 -less than 40" category, followed by 25.3% in the "40-49" age range, and 10.5% in the "50 or older" age bracket. The survey's results on experience, moreover, suggested that Among those polled 49.8% of study participants have prior work experience "6-8 years", followed by 29.7% have experience "3-5 years", then 18.6% have experience "9-11 years", and those with experience "12 years and more" constituted 2.0% and made up the smallest share of the study's overall sample.

6.2 Exploratory Factor Analysis

to bring down a lot of variables to a reasonable subset, exploratory factor analysis was employed. The purpose of this statistical technique is to reveal the underlying structure of a sizable dataset (Norris & Lecavalier. 2010). Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) coefficients are computed and should be very close to 1 to indicate that an analysis is adequate.

The adequacy condition is satisfied by the KMO results presented in table 2 of this study. In addition, the Chi-Square values for each variable were statistically significant, with p-values lower than 0.001 according to Bartlett's test of sphericity. This finding proves that there is a strong connection between every possible pair of variables. Therefore, the data sample size is adequate for this research.

Table 2: Results of Exploratory Factor Analysis

Variable	Statement Items	Factor loadings	KMO Measure of Sample Adequacy (>0.5)	Bartlett's Test of Sphericity		Items confirmed	Items dropped	Cum % of loading
				Chi Square	Sig. (<.10)			
Just in Time (JIT)	JIT1	.861	.781	1008.134	.000	4	0	73.344
	JIT2	.870						
	JIT3	.857						
	JIT4	.838						
Continuous Improvement (CI)	CI1	.862	.814	840.827	.000	4	0	70.475
	CI2	.878						
	CI3	.839						
	CI4	.775						
Autonomation	Autonmn1	.847	.754	833.661	.000	4	0	69.004
	Autonmn2	.837						
	Autonmn3	.830						
	Autonmn4	.809						
Total Productive	TPM1	.809	.683	537.121	.000	3	0	74.029
	TPM2	.866						

Maintenance (TPM)	TPM3	.904						
Value Stream Mapping (VSM)	VSM1	.857	.873	1130.030	.000	5	0	67.666
	VSM2	.846						
	VSM3	.831						
	VSM4	.811						
	VSM5	.766						
Cellular Manufacturing (CM)	CM1	.901	.875	1730.621	.000	5	0	75.709
	CM2	.762						
	CM3	.882						
	CM4	.888						
	CM5	.909						
Single Minute Exchange of Die (SMED)	SMED1	.845	.755	485.902	.000	4	0	59.471
	SMED2	.807						
	SMED3	.727						
	SMED4	.697						
Digital Supply Chains (DSC)	DSC1	.817	.768	550.343	.000	4	0	62.132
	DSC2	.830						
	DSC3	.753						
	DSC4	.749						

For this study, we used the minimum allowed loading factor of 0.5. A total of four items are contained in Component 1 (Just in Time), four Things are categorized under Component 2. (Continuous Improvement), four Things are categorized under Component 3. (Autonomation), three items are assigned into Component 4 (Total Productive Maintenance), five items are assigned into Component 5 (Value Stream Mapping), five items are assigned into Component 6 (Cellular Manufacturing), four items are assigned into Component 7 (Single Minute Exchange of Die), and finally, four items are assigned into Component 8 (Digital Supply Chains) as summarized in Table 2. Thus, total 33 items have been used for further analysis.

6.3 Reliability Analysis

Before proceeding with the evaluation and the Cronbach Alpha values were accustomed to check the dependability of the data. Nunnally and Bernstein (1994) say that for novel scales, an alpha as low as 0.60 is fine. Alternatively, an a recognized scale with a 0.70 alpha is typically required to ensure internal consistency. Using Cronbach's alpha, set at 0.7 for this research.

The alpha values for JIT (.878), CI (.859), Autonomation (.847), TPM (.824), VSM (.879), CM (.914), SMED (.771) and DSC (.796) indicated that There was sufficient internal consistency between the components to create a reliable scale. Table 3 displays Values of Cronbach's alpha that are higher than the bare minimum of 0.7.

Table 3: Results of the Reliability Examination

	Independent Variable	Cronbach Alpha
1	Just in Time (JIT)	.878
2	Continuous Improvement (CI)	.859
3	Autonomation	.847
4	Total Productive Maintenance (TPM)	.824
5	Value Stream Mapping (VSM)	.879
6	Cellular Manufacturing (CM)	.914
7	Single Minute Exchange of Die (SMED)	.771
8	Digital Supply Chains (DSC)	.796
	Over all Questionnaire	.972

6.4 Correlation Analysis

The respondents' opinions on the various digital supply chain and lean manufacturing dimensions were analyzed using the mean. The standard deviation is a measure of dispersion that helps us see how far the answers are from the mean. In addition, Pearson's correlation coefficients were taken from the data in order to confirm the multi-collinearity as among electronic supply chain dimensions along with the inter-correlation among the variables in the research.

According to Table 4's averages, all of the dimensions of LM fall between moderate and high in respect to their relative importance. The findings suggested that TPM (M= 4.2584, SD=.78983 ranked first, and VSM (M= 4.2354, SD= 0.73456)placed second, followed by SMED (M=4.2303, SD=0.64956) and JIT (M=4.0966, SD=.75975). The rest dimensions are also at a high relative importance level as CM (M= 4.0424, SD= 0.70110) was situated in the fifth status, independence (M= 4.0262, SD= 0.83491) in the sixth rank, then CI (M= 3.5955, SD= 0.93206) It was situated in the seventh and final place. The DSC is also at a high relative importance level(M= 4.2407, SD= 0.66939).

The correlation study's findings demonstrate that there is a significant relationship between each of the variables. The entire variables have a strong association with each of the eight variables looked at. Correlation between " SMED" and " VSM" is the highest (0.926), followed by .896 between DSC and VSM at second ranked and .895between CM and VSM. While TPM and CI possess the least meaningful connections (0.540).

Table 4: Correlations between proposed variables

	Mean	Std. Deviation	JIT	CI	Autonomation	TPM	VSM	CM	SMED	DSC
JIT	4.0966	.75975	1							
CI	3.5955	.93206	.589**	1						
Autonomation	4.0262	.83491	.705**	.660**	1					
TPM	4.2584	.78983	.787**	.540**	.725**	1				
VSM	4.2354	.73456	.815**	.585**	.741**	.785**	1			
CM	4.0424	.70110	.889**	.795**	.885**	.877**	.895**	1		
SMED	4.2303	.64956	.781**	.576**	.672**	.745**	.926**	.844**	1	
DSC	4.2407	.66939	.754**	.549**	.664**	.706**	.896**	.814**	.893**	1

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

6.5 Regression Analysis

The link between the independent and dependent variables is determined by the predictor-criterion utilizing enter analysis of regression. The regression analysis has been performed between Digital Supply Chains (DSC) and dimensions of lean manufacturing (LM). In the study, the DSC has been taken as independent variable and the dimensions of LM has been taken as dependent variable. It was done to measure the influence of independent variable Digital Supply Chains (DSC) on Constant Improvement (CI), Just-in-Time (JIT), Autonomation, Value Stream Mapping (VSM), Cellular Manufacturing (CM), and Total Productive Maintenance (TPM) and SMED stands for Single Minute Exchange of Die.

6.5.1 Dimensions of Lean Manufacturing (LM) as Dependent Variables

Several distinct regression models are created and examined for the Dimensions of Lean Manufacturing (JIT, CI, Autonomation, TPM, VSM, CM and SMED) as dependent variables. Digital Supply Chains (DSC) was independently determined and taken separately variable within regression models that use Digital Marketing (DM) in India as the dependent variable shown in table 5.

Based on the findings of the enter Table 5's regression analysis, seven factors of lean manufacturing (JIT, CI, Autonomation, TPM, VSM, CM and SMED) were found to be significantly influenced by Digital Supply Chains (DSC). Using the R square values of 0.568, 0.302, 0.440, 0.499, 0.803, 0.663 and 0.797, we can see that Digital Supply Chains (DSC) is capable of explaining each of these seven variables separately (JIT, CI, Autonomation, TPM, VSM, CM and SMED) to the degree of 56.8%, 30.2%, 44%, 49.9%, 80.3%, 66.3% and 79.7% respectively.

The regression model's ANOVA results are shown, proving its validity with a 95% confidence level. Table 5 presents a concise summary of the associated coefficients, revealing beta values of Digital Supply Chains (DSC) with JIT, CI, Autonomation, TPM, VSM, CM and SMED factors as .754, .549, .664, .706, .896, .814 and .893. Consequently, the outcomes of which are often suggestive of the significance of Digital Supply Chains (DSC) on dimensions of Lean Manufacturing (JIT, CI, Autonomation, TPM, VSM, CM and SMED).

Table 5: Regression Result- Digital Marketing as Dependent Variable

Independent Variable	Dependent Variable	Model Summary		ANOVA ^a			Coefficients ^a		
		R	R Square	Mean Square	F	Sig.	St. Coefficients Beta	t	Sig.
DSC	JIT	.754 ^a	.568	149.937	600.541	.000 ^b	.754	24.506	.000
DSC	CI	.549 ^a	.302	119.845	197.174	.000 ^b	.549	14.042	.000
DSC	Auton	.664 ^a	.440	140.280	358.805	.000 ^b	.664	18.942	.000
DSC	TPM	.706 ^a	.499	142.127	453.322	.000 ^b	.706	21.291	.000
DSC	VSM	.896 ^a	.803	197.985	1857.552	.000 ^b	.896	43.099	.000
DSC	CM	.814 ^a	.663	148.980	897.959	.000 ^b	.814	29.966	.000
DSC	SMED	.893 ^a	.797	153.606	1786.082	.000 ^b	.893	42.262	.000

7. TEST RESULTS FOR HYPOTHESES

Regression Analysis was used to quantify the strength of the correlation between the various hypotheses, and their inclusion in the model's estimation was a key step in the statistical study. The SPSS-calculated values for all of the hypotheses are presented in Table 6. This evidence suggests that they correspond to the theoretically predicted associations. Table 6 demonstrates that all seven hypotheses proposed within the study's conceptual framework were acceptable.

Table 6: Summary of Test Results for Hypotheses

Hy. No.	Independent Variables	to	Dependent Variables	R-Square	Beta Coefficient	t-value	Sig Value	Status of Hypotheses
H1	DSC	→	JIT	.568	.754	24.506	.000	Accepted
H2	DSC	→	CI	.302	.549	14.042	.000	Accepted
H3	DSC	→	Auton	.440	.664	18.942	.000	Accepted
H4	DSC	→	TPM	.499	.706	21.291	.000	Accepted
H5	DSC	→	VSM	.803	.896	43.099	.000	Accepted

H6	DSC	→	CM	.663	.814	29.966	.000	Accepted
H7	DSC	→	SMED	.797	.893	42.262	.000	Accepted

8. DISCUSSION

This study's goal was to investigate how digital supply chains (DSC) affect lean manufacturing (LM) practices dimensions. The effect of DSC on the seven facets of lean production is evaluated (JIT, CI, Autonomation, TPM, VSM, CM and SMED). The findings demonstrated that DSC is useful in conjunction with the seven LM dimensions used in this investigation. This results of the study added to the existing body of work that has concentrated on DSC and LM.

The sample in this study Verifies that the incorporation of electronic devices into their DSC has improved their aptitudes and helped to ease the movement of data and supplies through these channels. The results demonstrated that by incorporating LM techniques into their manufacturing processes, they were Capable of reacting more quickly to modifications in consumer demand. These methods greatly aided production allocation and helped cut down on wasteful spending and squandered resources in manufacturing facilities.

Using digital tools, we can streamline our conversations and exchanges. Materials can be moved more efficiently between stores and warehouses, whether they are raw materials or manufactured goods. One of the most crucial aspects of LM is the on-time production system, which is bolstered by this. Production proofs are also supported by the digital technologies. Engineers can run virtual tests on the product with no risk or expense. Prototype development and testing are aided by this method.

Supply chain digital technologies can aid in error detection in real time, which is a huge boon to continuous improvement initiatives. It's useful for pinpointing the root of the problem and coming up with viable alternatives to fix it. It bolsters LM mechanisms and stops operations from lagging behind due to a buildup of hidden errors. Managers can then update their processes in light of the best option they've chosen. These findings agree with those of Liu and Chiu (2021). He emphasized the positive effect DSC integration has on business output. And the improvement in performance is determined by The particular application of supply chains utilizing digital technologies. According to Haddud&Khare's (2020), digital supply chains have a positive effect on manufacturing flexibility. DSC practices help ensure the timely implementation of the production strategy, as confirmed by the research of Montoya et al. (2021). DSC, as discovered by Haddud and Khare (2018), help boost the efficiency of lean manufacturing methods. This is due to the fact that significant tools used in DSC aid enterprises in minimizing waste throughout production.

This research shows that DSC is effective in enhancing the seven lean principles investigated. This research adds to the existing literature by pinpointing specific ways in which DSC facilitates the implementation of JIT, CI, Autonomation, TPM, VSM, CM, and SMED. Findings from this study Describe how a crucial facilitator of lean operations is to the adoption of Technologies related to Industry 4.0 (Erro-Garcés, 2019) and contribute

significantly to the theoretical understanding of how to integrate Technologies related to Industry 4.0 (De Sousa Jabbour et al., 2018).

9. CONCLUSIONS

The supply chain will eventually be fully digitalized. Where to begin is the question. Managers can see quick returns on their technology investments by targeting those areas with the greatest potential impact. This research closes a gap in the body of knowledge by looking into how DSC can aid in the use of lean principles in manufacturing companies. Those companies that are on the fence about implementing greater levels of their supply chains' digitization can benefit greatly from this investigation.

This study offers a wealth of information about the possible effects of DSC on businesses, especially in regards to the seven LM dimensions that were studied (JIT, CI, Autonomation, TPM, VSM, CM and SMED). In sum, the data in this study can be a valuable asset to the DSC. This work can additionally function as a foundation for upcoming research that investigate various facets of DSC's usefulness to businesses.

10. MANAGERIAL IMPLICATIONS

The study's findings offer a foundation on which to rely digital supply chains that will play an important role in boosting business performance. Singh et al. (2019) suggestions' are backed up by the results from this research. Singh et al. (2019) highlighted that Companies will be encouraged to adopt a wide range of the Fourth Industrial Revolution technologies because of the recent creation of new cognitive technology.

This paper helps satisfy the need for additional research that employs DSC to investigate LM practices. The work of Mayr et al. (2018) centres on the incorporation of LM procedures in conjunction with Industry 4.0 tools. Duarte and Cruz-Machado (2017) stressed the significance of exhibiting flexible supply chain features. The study's findings offer useful information for business leaders looking to optimize their digital supply chains in terms of profit and efficiency.

11. LIMITATIONS AND RECOMMENDATION

Participants' opinions on several foreseeable consequences of DSC on selected LM practices were investigated. Future studies may use either open-ended or multiple-choice survey questions to investigate the possible effects of the seven practices. This may cause researchers to report effects that differ from those found in this analysis. Additionally, participants had to be employed in the construction industry. Accordingly, we recommend that future studies take into account collecting participant feedback from a variety of experts in the field. As a result, researchers will be able to glean more actionable insights from professionals and practitioners who are likely to be directly involved with the adoption and operation of DSC in a variety of industries.

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